

Federated Data Sharing and Analysis for Social Utility

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WPL: Canary Bit (CBIT)

Author(s): Nicolae Paladi, Nenad Gligoric, Ivan Djurkov, Luis Búrdalo Rapa, Timo Leppänen

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Status, Change History and Glossary

Table 1 Status Change History

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Table 3 List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

ADT	Application Description Template
AHI	Apnea-hypopnea index
API	Application Programming Interface
APT	Advanced Persistent Threat
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
EEG	Electroencephalography
FE	Functional Encryption
HE	Homomorphic Encryption
HHE	Hybrid Homomorphic Encryption
IoC	Indicator of Compromise
ML	Machine Learning
OSA	Obstructive sleep apnea
PPG	Photoplethysmography
PSG	Polysomnography
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TTP	Tactics, techniques, procedures
UAC	User Account Control
REM	Rapid Eye Movement

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Executive Summary

Project HARPOCRATES investigates technologies, tools and solutions for secure and privacy-preserving data processing and sharing. We use two demonstrators to validate the security solutions developed in the project. The demonstrators are (i) *threat intelligence generation and sharing between local authorities*, exploring exchange of threat intelligence information between two regional governments in EU member states (Italy and Spain) and (ii) *collaborative use of Machine Learning in Sleep Medicine*, exploring exchange of sleep research data between three research institutions located in three EU member states (Finland, France, and Germany). Solutions developed in the project will be applied to these demonstrators and subsequently presented.

This document contains the technical requirements solicited in close collaboration with the demonstrator partners, architecture of the HARPOCRATES solution toolbox containing the enablers developed by the technical partners, as well as the testing plan for the solutions. The two demonstrators described in this document represent vastly different technological prerequisites, data models and operational constraints. This is reflected both in their overall descriptions, as well as in the threat models, requirements, and target operations. Their detailed description in this document is an important early contribution of the project. They *highlight* the stringent requirements towards privacy-preserving solutions based on practical challenges, as well *challenge* to various implicit and explicit assumptions.

The document also describes the enablers to be developed in HARPOCRATES to address the demonstrator requirements. The enablers described in this document reflect the variety of complementary approaches that need to be combined and tailored according to the specific context and peculiarities of the application use cases.

This document reconciles the wide range of demonstrator requirements with the limitations of the state-of-the-art technologies used in the enablers. It also serves as a roadmap for the remainder of the project in the implementation of the HARPOCRATES solution toolbox and implementation of the demonstrators.

1 Introduction

This section introduces the document, presents its structure, goals and scope.

Project HARPOCRATES aims to achieve ambitious objectives towards the long-term goal of enabling digitally blind processing of arbitrary data using complex processing functions. Achieving this long-term goal is a major undertaking with several initial activities that must be conducted, such as:

- **implementing** the technological enablers for confidential processing and sharing data and identifying its limitations with the current state of the art;
- **understanding** the documenting the constraints and limitations on the quality and structure of data to be processed;
- **contextualising** confidential data processing and sharing in terms of legal constraints and practical end-user requirements; and,
- **applying** the technological enablers in practical scenarios to demonstrate their practical use.

While the activities listed above have their specifics and prerequisites, they are connected in a logical roadmap that will be implemented in the HARPOCRATES project. One of the main expected outcomes of the project is developing novel cybersecurity algorithms and implementing these algorithms in the HARPOCRATES solution box. This is meant to be a modular artefact that can be adapted and reused in industrial settings, follow-up research and innovation actions, or as an educational tool. This document describes the organisation of the target system.

1.1 Contribution

This document describes the **architecture** of the expected solution toolbox implementation in the HARPOCRATES project (“**the toolbox**”). The document describes the components, protocols, integrations, and demonstrators, along with a set of requirements collected early on and guiding the implementation of the project.

1.2 Goals

This deliverable pursues three main goals that are relevant to stakeholders both internal and external to the project, as follows:

- **Inform** the reader about the technical components part of the toolbox, their features, and limitations, as well their communication interfaces and integration, the rationale behind the implemented features, and the structure of the overall systems.
- **Document** the efforts behind designing and developing the toolbox, as well as illustrate the intellectual journey starting from the project vision, through the gradual

understanding of practical technical, legal, and organisational constraints, to the final implementation of the toolbox artefacts.

- **Guide** project partners and external stakeholders in their efforts to implement and subsequently extend the toolbox, as well as eventually to implement or otherwise apply it in other contexts.

1.3 Scope

This deliverable is limited to the description of the toolbox components, their interactions and integrations, requirements guiding the toolbox architecture, and operational aspects in terms of testing and evaluation. Description of other aspects such as use of the toolbox components in practical applications (“demonstrators”), discussions and plans about future work and any additional requirements to the toolbox components are explicitly excluded from this document and may be addressed elsewhere.

1.4 Organisation

Beyond this point, the document is structured as follows: Section 2 describes the **technological background** of the toolbox components. Section 3 describes the **methodology** adopted in designing the architecture and adopting design decisions. Section 4 describes the **requirements** collected from demonstrator partners that guide the design and development of the toolbox components. Section 5 describes the **HARPOCRATES platform architecture**. Section 6 describes the approach and structure of the **integration testing** of the toolbox components. Section 7 describes the **evaluation** of the toolbox components from several perspectives. Finally, Section 8 **concludes** this document with an overview of the outcomes of the activity.

2 Background

This section introduces technical and contextual background that helps understand the components of the HARPOCRATES architecture. It also briefly touches upon the state of the art relevant to the different components.

2.1 Demonstrator Verticals

2.1.1 Threat intelligence generation and sharing between local authorities (*Threat Intelligence Demonstrator*)

In today's digital age, cybersecurity has emerged as an essential cornerstone for governments, private entities, and individuals alike. As society's reliance on digital systems has grown, so too has the complexity and volume of cyber threats. Governments face risks of state-sponsored attacks, espionage, and disruptions to critical infrastructure. Private companies, regardless of size, grapple with potential financial losses, reputation damage, and operational disruptions. Individuals are not spared either, with threats to personal data, financial assets, and privacy looming large. Particularly concerning in this landscape are Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs) — sophisticated, well-funded, and prolonged cyberattacks that aim to steal, spy, or sabotage. APTs present a significant security challenge, even for organisations with robust security measures and up-to-date practices. These threats, often orchestrated by experienced and highly skilled attackers, with the potential to inflict severe damage on numerous systems.

The inner nature of APTs makes them difficult to detect and, since they are usually tailored to a specific target, it is not possible to build a straight detection rule which raises an alarm each time they appear. As a result, it is common when dealing with APTs to rely on anomaly detection methods and techniques. Attending to different features, these techniques learn or model the behaviour of a system in normal circumstances, so that an alarm is raised when the observed behaviour of the system is too different from the expected one, previously learned or modelled. Anomaly thresholds, which determine when an observed behaviour is considered normal or not, are also set for each system. This approach is very useful and reliable, especially thanks to the use of Machine Learning (ML), which makes it possible to learn the normal behaviour of a system by tracking it under normal conditions.

In addition to training and using ML-based anomaly detection models locally (within an organisation), sharing them can be a forward-looking and efficient way to exchange cyber threat intelligence. Traditional threat intelligence often revolves around sharing specific indicators of compromise (IoCs) such as IP addresses, domain names, or file hashes. These are specific, static, and can easily be altered by adversaries to evade detection. Anomaly

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detection models, however, encapsulate behaviour patterns of threats. These are harder for adversaries to change without significantly altering their *tactics, techniques, or procedures* (TTPs). Also, by using shared models, organisations can detect threats based on similar criteria, leading to a standardised understanding and response to certain threat behaviours.

Sharing trained models is an attractive and reliable option for many organisations since it provides the benefits of shared knowledge without directly sharing potentially sensitive data. However, training these models still requires big amounts of potentially sensitive data, such as raw logs or data of a user or organisation. Sharing these data usually requires the consent of the company (or its employees). Also, companies and individual users are reluctant to share data regarding the ways in which they have been attacked, especially when attacks were successful, because they do not want their public image to be damaged.

Some current commercial products already offer capabilities such as those mentioned. But those are proprietary solutions that rely on the manufacturer's access to sensitive data from the organisation and users. This exposes the organisation to new risks, as it relies completely on the good practices applied by the manufacturer. Additionally, manufacturers do not share information with each other, so the protection provided by the security tool is always limited.

In HARPOCRATES demonstrators the aim is to build a public and open system that allows different organisations to participate with the confidence that, although sensitive data may be accessed, its privacy is never compromised guaranteed by the design of the system.

To achieve that, the HARPOCRATES demonstrators make use of the novel cryptographic technologies developed in this project to collect and share sensitive information about users and process behaviour within the computer systems of each organisation without compromising their privacy. Another goal is to apply privacy-preserving Machine Learning algorithms over those datasets to extract intelligence on new threats based on the detection of patterns of attacks and anomaly inference.

2.1.1.1 Vertical Threat Model of the Threat Intelligence Demonstrator

Some of the most relevant threats that can be detected by monitoring users' activity in the endpoint using are the following:

- **Malware Execution:** By monitoring process creation with full command line and hashes, the execution of known or suspicious malware can be detected. This can be particularly useful for catching variants of malware by looking for anomalies or patterns typical of malicious software.

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- **Lateral Movements:** Monitoring remote process creations and network connections can reveal attempts by attackers to move laterally within a network, especially if a process starts from an uncommon or unexpected parent process.
- **Persistence Mechanisms:** Monitoring changes in certain registry keys or start-up folders commonly used by malware to ensure they remain on the system after reboot can be useful for detecting persistence attempts.
- **Process Hollowing and Injection:** Capturing and monitoring detailed information about process creation and termination makes it possible to identify suspicious parent-child process relationships or anomalies can reveal malicious injection of code into legitimate processes carried out by malware to evade detection.
- **Data Exfiltration:** Sysmon logs network connections, which can help identify unexpected or suspicious data transfers, especially if they involve uncommon ports or protocols.
- **Credential Dumping:** Monitoring endpoint activity looking for the typical signs of tools like Mimikatz or processes accessing the memory of lsass.exe can help detect attackers trying to extract credentials from the system after having compromised it.
- **File Tampering:** Monitoring file creation and modification, especially in critical system areas can help in detecting ransomware activity, unauthorised changes, or the dropping of malicious payloads.
- **DNS Anomalies:** Monitoring DNS queries can help detect suspicious domain requests or domains associated with Command & Control (C2) servers.
- **Driver Loading:** Detecting unexpected or malicious kernel driver loading can give insights into rootkits or other low-level threats.
- **Memory and Disk Anomalies:** Monitoring for unexpected interactions with the system's memory or disk can indicate the presence of threats that reside solely in memory (fileless malware) or attempts to directly access the disk.
- **Bypassing UAC:** Monitoring process creation can also help detect when an attacker tries to bypass User Account Control (UAC) to elevate privileges.
- **Unexpected Parent-Child Process Relationships:** Monitoring process creation can help detect when a typically benign process spawns an unexpected child process, which may be indicative of a malware trying to use a legitimate process to launch its payload.

2.1.1.2 Envisioned situation of the threat intelligence demonstrator

In this demonstrator, we propose building a threat intelligence sharing scenario between two European regions in Italy and Spain. On the one hand, each region represents a significant volume of data that can be processed, constituting a very relevant information sample. On the other hand, currently governments are targeted by attackers and are exposed to great risks,

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as they provide important services such as health, education, and social services. Thus, both organisations would benefit from an advanced anonymization/encryption mechanism that allows them to share cyber threat intelligence which may be based on private and sensitive information while respecting the privacy of their organisation and users' data.

For the demonstrator, we propose collecting events that occur on users' computers captured through **Windows Sysmon**¹. Windows Sysmon is a tool for the Windows operating system which runs as a service that logs detailed system activity, such as process creations, network connections, privilege escalation or changes to file creation time. Since data gathered from different users depicts the real-time status of what is happening on the computer systems on each organization's network, it is possible to train different ML models to learn the normal behaviour of well-known system processes, such as `rundll32.exe`, or user processes, such as `chrome.exe`. In this way, when one or more processes in the system start behaving in an unexpected way, a cybersecurity alert can be raised for an analyst to review that process.

In this approach, there are some relevant aspects to consider. First, since each process has a different purpose and utility, their inner variability in terms of behaviour can also be very different. Also, the way in which some processes behave may be very different in each company. In fact, this variation can be relevant even considering different users within the same company. As a result, some processes may be easier to model than others. Thus, the amount of available data regarding each process execution may be significantly different for each process. Second, not all system and user processes are equally relevant in terms of threat detection, so it is important to select which processes to model in order to make the final solution feasible and useful for anomaly and threat detection.

2.1.2 Collaborative use of Machine Learning in Sleep Medicine (*Sleep Medicine Demonstrator*)

Machine and deep learning-related research have gained great interest during the last years in the field of sleep medicine. Research projects utilising these methods need to exploit a huge amount of clinically sensitive data. This includes usual medical data like gender, age, social status, medication, medical diagnoses, and specific for sleep medicine, digital sleep recordings with physiological signals such as brain waves (electroencephalogram), eye movements (electrooculogram), muscular activity (electromyogram) heart rhythm (electrocardiogram), respiration (respiratory flow, respiratory effort, oxygen content in the blood), body position, sound audio recording (snoring, speaking during sleep), and video

¹ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/sysinternals/downloads/sysmon>

recordings of night behaviour (like sleep waking, or acting out dreams). The recording of signals together with sound and video is called 'polysomnography'. This raises several issues, such as the openness of research, privacy concerns, and security of data, and the importance to find a balance between them. Several sleep medicine applications use a transmission of the sleep recording, the polysomnogram, to a remote server which does some signal processing, and then the processed polysomnogram together with processing results, is transmitted back to the sender, the medical centre carrying out the sleep investigation.

2.1.2.1 Vertical Threat Model of the Sleep Medicine Demonstrator

The demonstrator will utilise data consisting of sleep recordings, a subset of signals mentioned above (i.e., electroencephalography, electrooculography, electromyography, breathing signals, oximetry signals, snoring (audio), sleeping position, respiratory effort, and possibly the nocturnal video recording), patient medical records and questionnaires related to sleep disorders in text format (word, excel, etc.), collected within the H2020 SLEEPREVOLUTION project. This specifically relates to the registry of sleep recordings collected by the ESADA group, being part of SLEEPREVOLUTION. In addition, previous EU project results were used from the SIESTA project to include sleep recordings from healthy volunteers. The sleep medicine procedures involve detecting deep sleep, REM sleep, awakenings from sleep, sleep apnea events, body movement events. Next, the sleep medicine procedures generate a summarizing report including percentage calculations (e.g. percent of deep sleep of total sleep time), time measures (e.g. the time needed from sleep beginning to the first REM phase), and ratios (e.g. number of apnea events per hour of sleep time), The aim of the demonstrator is to illustrate that after the encryption the sleep recordings can be handled and analysed similarly (using complex analytics and ML techniques) to the non-encrypted data.

2.1.2.2 Envisioned situation of the sleep medicine demonstrator

Currently, research projects are supposed to follow the FAIR data principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) and the recent European Commission's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR,2016/679). However, following the GDPR hinders the implementation of FAIR and makes data sharing between clinical or research institutions highly difficult, especially in the case of retrospective data. Ideally, data sharing should contain three steps: (1) data encryption, (2) data sharing with secured platforms, and (3) secure data storage. However, data encryption has not received the attention it deserves albeit being one of the key elements: if for any reason the two other steps fail, data encryption ensures that the data is still protected, and identification of individuals is not possible. Thus, having sophisticated and validated data encryption algorithms available would be highly valuable for the whole research community. Additionally, performing complex analytics and Machine

Learning operations on the encrypted data is also desired to facilitate the joint exploitation of this securely shared data.

2.2 Technology Background

2.2.1 Cryptographic primitives

2.2.1.1 Functional Encryption

Functional Encryption (FE) is an emerging cryptographic technique that enables selective computations over encrypted data. In short, it allows a user (e.g., a data analyst) with a specific functional decryption key to determine a certain result of encrypted data without gaining access to the underlying data. Generally, FE schemes provide a key generation algorithm that outputs decryption keys with remarkable capabilities. More precisely, each decryption key is associated with a function (i.e., an operation). In contrast to traditional cryptographic techniques, using this decryption key on a ciphertext does not recover the corresponding plaintext, but directly the result of the computation—thus keeping the initial value private.

Unfortunately, while FE seems to be a perfect fit for Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning (PPML), most of the work revolves around constructing generic schemes that do not support specific functions and are designed for devices without any resource constraints. While the concept of FE has the potential to be used for creative and useful applications, there remain concerns about its real-world applicability.

Advantages: fast computation, selective operations. Suited to Multi-Party Computation with access control.

Limitations: operations restricted to inner product (i.e., addition) and quadratic polynomials (i.e., a single multiplication) on integers. Often requires trusted authority.

Current progress: we are working on an FE scheme for hypnograms. The features are:

- Allow an analyst to know how many times a specific value appears in the hypnogram (e.g., the number of 0 in the hypnogram).
- Do not require a trusted authority. The patient encrypts her hypnogram and stores them in a server – the hospital for example. Without the knowledge of the message, the server can send the results to an analyst, after checking their credentials.

2.2.1.2 Hybrid Homomorphic Encryption

HHE is a new approach employing specific symmetric encryption scheme which allows the data owners to encrypt their data using a symmetric key (or key stream). Next,

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homomorphically encrypt this key by an HE scheme. Finally, data owners can send the symmetric ciphertexts and the HE-encrypted key to a powerful server or cloud to do the homomorphic computation over the ciphertexts. Using HHE schemes will decrease the communication costs, but it will increase the computation costs on the server side. Therefore, using HHE is a trade-off between communication costs and computation costs.

There are three different families of HHE stream ciphers based on different HE schemes, which were designed to work with different data types. We summarized the specification of each one in Table 1.

Table 5 Current state-of-the-art HHE stream ciphers

Stream Cipher	HE Scheme	Data Type	Library	Language
Pasta	BGV, BFV	Integer	SEAL, HElib	C, C++
HERA, Rubato	CKKS	Floating Point	Lattigo	Golang
Elisabeth	TFHE	Binary	Concrete	Rust

In our 3-party scenario, first, the Data Analyst generates the HHE keys. Second, each user generates its own symmetric key and encrypts the data with this key. Next, the user encrypts the symmetric key using HE scheme, and the HE public key. Finally, the user sends both the symmetrically encrypted data and homomorphically encrypted key to the CSP (Cloud Service Provider). The CSP transfers the symmetric ciphertext into a homomorphic ciphertext and then proceed with performing the computations. After running evaluation over encrypted data, the CSP sends the results back to the Data Analyst, who can decrypt them using HHE secret key.

Advantage: Preserving the privacy of users' data, less communication overhead (smaller ciphertext).

Limitations: Each scheme is limited to a specific data type, the size of inputs is limited to the plaintext space size.

Current progress: We are trying to implement different ML scenarios using HHE schemes

2.2.2 Privacy-Preserving Operations

2.2.2.1 Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning

Machine Learning (ML) models are widely used in various applications like medical diagnosis, pattern recognition, and credit risk assessment. However, the use of ML can compromise user privacy, leading to a growing concern for maintaining confidentiality, privacy, and user trust. Privacy-preserving machine learning (PPML) techniques have been developed to address these concerns and offer technological advancements while also aiming for societal impact.

PPML ensures the protection of user privacy and secure utilization of data, preventing the disclosure of confidential information. Different techniques, including secure cryptographic schemes, distributed approaches, hybrid methods, and data modification approaches, have been proposed and implemented for achieving PPML. In the HARPOCRATES project, our focus is on the cryptographic approaches.

HARPOCRATES considers as cryptographic solution Homomorphic Encryption (HE) that allows third parties, such as users or service providers, to perform computations on encrypted data, including addition, multiplication, and bitwise operations. This capability has enabled the development of new applications, such as Machine Learning as a Service (MLaaS), where data is encrypted and processed in the cloud. Additionally, HE can be used to maintain the privacy of the ML model by encrypting its parameters. However, widespread adoption of HE has been hindered by computational complexity and increased ciphertext size, which poses challenges for practical implementation. To overcome these issues, researchers have explored the concept of Hybrid Homomorphic Encryption (HHE), which combines symmetric ciphers with HE to improve usability.

2.2.2.2 Federated Learning

Federated Learning (FL) is a distributed learning approach where multiple participants (*contributors*) collaborate to collectively train a Machine Learning model without sharing their local data directly. Instead of sending raw data to a central server, FL involves sending model parameters or updates between the central server and the contributors. This unique approach offers several advantages, including privacy preservation, reduced communication overhead, and the ability to harness the power of decentralised resources. Below we outline the key components of a Federated Learning system:

- a) **Centralised Server:** In federated learning, a centralised server plays a crucial role in coordinating the learning process. It aggregates model updates from the participating devices and communicates the updated model parameters back to them.
- b) **Contributing parties:** A set of contributing parties possess local data that contributes to the training process. Such contributing parties can be either devices (such as smartphones, edge devices, or IoT devices), or organisations (Regione Veneto and SARGA in the context of the HARPOCRATES project). The contributing parties train their models locally using their data and share model updates with the central server.
- c) **Communication Protocol:** Effective communication protocols are necessary to ensure secure and efficient transmission of model updates between the central server and participating devices. Best practice network security approaches can be employed to protect sensitive data during transmission.
- d) **Local Model Training:** Each participating contributor trains its local model using its local data. This process can involve traditional machine learning algorithms or deep learning techniques, depending on the complexity of the task at hand.
- e) **Model Aggregation:** The central server collects the model updates from the participating contributors and performs aggregation techniques like averaging or weighted averaging to generate an updated global model. This updated model is then sent back to the participating contributors for further iterations.

Federated Learning brings several important advantages that have determined its application in the HARPOCRATES project.

- a) **Privacy Preservation:** Federated learning overcomes the need to share raw data, addressing privacy concerns associated with centralised machine learning approaches. Local data remains on the participating contributors, significantly reducing the risk of data breaches or unauthorised access.
- b) **Reduced Communication Costs:** By avoiding the transmission of raw data, federated learning minimises the communication overhead. This is particularly beneficial in scenarios with limited bandwidth or high latency, such as edge computing environments or networks with low connectivity.
- c) **Scalability and Resource Efficiency:** Federated learning enables distributed training on a massive scale by leveraging the computational power of numerous participating contributors. This decentralised approach eliminates the need for transferring large amounts of data to a central server, making it well-suited for scenarios involving massive datasets or geographically dispersed contributors.
- d) **Continual Learning and Adaptation:** Federated learning allows for continual learning and adaptation to changing data distributions. With the ability to update models on local

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contributors, participants can adapt their models to real-time changes, improving performance and responsiveness.

DRAFT

3 Methodology

We follow a two-phase iterative approach to define and design the architecture of the HARPOCRATES toolbox. The two phases are *component definition* and *architecture design*, and they are described below.

Phase 1: Component definition

Understanding or defining the exact problems that HARPOCRATES aims to address is a critical prerequisite to implementing the HARPOCRATES toolbox. While the HARPOCRATES project application and subsequently the Grant Agreement serve as guiding documents, they both lack the necessary detail and can fall behind the scientific and technical advancements by the time the implementation work starts.

Thus, in the **first phase**, we focus our efforts on collecting inputs from the parties contributing their technical needs and envisaged solutions to the project, the *demonstrator partners* and *technical enabler providers* respectively. Input collection is done in three steps:

- 1. Initial context** helps to map the *needs* of demonstrator partners to the *capabilities* of technical enabler providers in the solution domain. In this step, project parties contribute data through one of the three types structured Typeform questionnaires (<https://typeform.com>): (i) *demonstrator and use case description*, (ii) *requirements collection*, (iii) *technical enabler description*. Data collected in this step is attached in Annex 1, 2².
- 2. Refinement** helps to match the expressed demonstrator partner needs with the capabilities of the enablers envisioned by the technical enabler providers. Moreover, this critical stage helps to clarify, discuss and ultimately align the expectations of participants with regards to the expected outcomes and extent of addressing demonstrator partner needs. Crucially, in this step the parties identify and explicitly describe limitations that may potentially require a reframing and renegotiation of the demonstrator partner needs and technical enabler capabilities. The result of this step is an alignment on the goals and expectations from the implementation of the technical enablers towards addressing original or reviewed demonstrator partner needs.
- 3. Component convergence** is a step to crystallise and formulate the demonstrator partner needs that will be addressed in the project as well as the functionality of the technical enablers that will be implemented in the project. It is possible - and indeed expected - that both the needs and the functionality are formulated in a layered structure, describing the *baseline*, *extended*, and *stretch-goal* solutions. This structure guides the evolution of the

² Note that while Typeform was chosen for its usability and versatile data collection functionality, subsequent feedback highlighted the need to change and review the provided input.

project in the cases when difficult or seemingly impossible challenges are overcome during the project, allowing to address more complex use case partner needs.

Phase 2: Architecture Design

The architecture design phase closely follows the pace of component definition and builds on its results as they emerge. An explicit decision is to avoid defining an architecture before having sufficient details about the problems to be solved, the context in which the HARPOCRATES toolbox can be useful and the capabilities and functionality of the technical enabler components. The rationale behind this decision is to avoid “drawing empty boxes” which diverts attention and adds unnecessary complications at the cost of tangible results and output. The architecture design phase consists of three phases: *initial components*, *compatibility*, and *architecture convergence*, as described below.

1. **Initial components** is the early understanding of the components, interfaces and structure of the toolbox during the first 6 months of the project. During this stage, contributors primarily operate on *assumptions* about use case needs, technical enabler components and their interactions, derived from the project application document and grant agreement document, based on earlier experiences and domain knowledge.

2. **Compatibility** is an exploration of the component functionality, their capability to address use case needs as defined in the *component convergence* stage described below, and their capability to interact with other components in the toolbox. In HARPOCRATES, the architecture definition and design in this stage is guided by the following three self-describing principles:

- It is a toolbox rather than a platform;
- Communication with REST APIs;
- Containerised components.

The outcome of this stage is an early draft of the architecture, presented early in the project, at the second regular project meeting. An initial agreement on the architectural principles and its overall structure builds a foundation for subsequent efforts.

3. **Architectural convergence** is achieved in the final step of the architecture definition effort. This is preceded by an **iterative** effort to ensure compatibility and interoperability among the technical enabler components and other ancillary components supporting the toolbox. The outcome of this stage is an architectural description that guides the development of the technical enabler components **addressing the needs and requirements** formulated by the use cases. Similar to the component convergence stage in Phase 1, the architectural description has a layered structure, with two output levels: architectural description document (*baseline*) and architecture-as-code (*stretch goal*).

4 Requirements of the HARPOCRATES Demonstrators

4.1 Threat Intelligence Demonstrator

4.1.1 Partners

S2, SARGA, VENETO

4.1.2 Overview

This demonstrator aims to develop new ways of information exchange between parties in the realm of cyber threat intelligence. The objective is to leverage on HARPOCRATES privacy preserving capabilities to avoid reluctance of organisations towards sharing such data, due to fears of disclosing technical details or reputational damage.

This demonstrator focuses on collecting data from the activity within the computers of the partners networks and process it through Privacy-preserving Machine Learning techniques developed in the project, to generate models to detect anomalies signalling potential cyber attacks to be investigated by the security operation teams.

4.1.3 Tasks

4.1.3.1 Identify anomalies indicating a potential attack

Anomalies identified in Sysmon log data captured from users activity can indicate the presence of an unknown attack. The detection can be done using a privacy-preserving machine learning model, capable to discern normal from anomalous behaviour. The model can become more effective if more log data is available for training.

4.1.3.1.1 Methodology

- Data acquisition
 - Recruitment of volunteers in SARGA and VENETO
 - Deployment of ARGOS Endpoint Collector in the computers of volunteers of SARGA and VENETO
 - Data recovering from SARGA and VENETO
 - Validation of the data recovering process
- Prototype development
 - Adaption of the anomaly detection prototype S2 GRUPO had before the HARPOCRATES project to the specific project demonstrator and its requirements
 - Development of PET for the anomaly detection prototype of the demonstrator
- Validation

- Selection of processes to be included in the demonstrator and attacks to be used for validation of results
- Attack injection in logs
- Validation experiments design
- Launching experiments with and without HARPOCRATES privacy enhancing capabilities
- Experimental results analysis

4.1.3.1.2 Data

Windows Sysmon log events, pre-processed to anonymise, normalize data and convert to integer values.

4.1.3.1.3 Technical Requirements

Functional requirements

- The system must capture Windows Sysmon events without interfering with users' activity.
- The system must be able to build a privacy-preserving ML model from a dataset of events to detect anomalies.
- Given a sequence of events (or a collection), the ML model must throw a probability confidence of an anomaly occurring.
- The system must show the anomalies detected on a dashboard.
- The system must return the anomalies in a log, so that these results can be correlated with other alerts or threat information provided by other cybersecurity tools.
- Given an anomalous detected event, the system must obtain a collection of potential IOCs from the preceding events to the one that raised the signal.
- Trained models must be uploaded and stored in the system encrypted in a privacy-preserving form.
- An authorized user should be able to disclose a collection of IOCs uploading and storing them in an encrypted form.

Security requirements

- The system must be able to build a privacy-preserving ML from a dataset of events to detect anomalies.
- Trained models must be uploaded and stored in the system encrypted in a privacy-preserving form.
- The system must grant access to the management dashboard only to authorized users.

- An authorized user should be able to disclose a collection of IOCs uploading and storing them in an encrypted form.

Performance requirements

- Given one event (or a collection) the system must check if there is a potential anomaly against the ML model in a reasonable time.
- Given one event (or a collection) the system must check if there is a potential anomaly against the collections of stored IOCs in a reasonable time.

4.1.3.1.4 Output

Trained machine learning model for anomaly detection in Sysmon logs.

4.2 Sleep medicine demonstrator

4.2.1 Partners

UMG, UEF, CHARITE

4.2.2 Overview

We aim to illustrate that by utilising the privacy preserving machine learning techniques developed in HARPOCRATES, encrypted sleep recordings can be handled and analysed similarly to non-encrypted data. We will demonstrate this by attempting to implement one or more clinically relevant data analysis tasks on encrypted sleep data.

4.2.3 Tasks

At the beginning of the HARPOCRATES, two specific tasks were planned (4.2.3.1-4.2.3.2):

- estimation of the severity of obstructive sleep apnea in short segments
- estimation of sleep stages and respiratory events from PSG recordings
- automatic exportation of PSG signals

However, these tasks were too complex to be performed in terms of available encryption schemes, thus, new tasks (4.2.3.3-4.2.3.6) were planned:

- estimation of presence of desaturations in short segments
- calculation of hypoxic load from short segments of SpO2 signals
- calculation of sleep fragmentation from hypnograms

These tasks were further simplified to meet the computational restrictions of HHE (2.2.1.2). The restrictions were the following:

- only integers could be used,

- calculations should only produce values between -65537 and 65537,
- the length of input vectors should be a few hundred numbers,
- non-linear operations cannot be used in neural networks.

4.2.3.1 Estimation of the severity of obstructive sleep apnea in short segments

The aim of this task was to automatically estimate the number of respiratory events (i.e. apneas and hypopneas) per hour of sleep. This is also called the apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) representing the severity of obstructive sleep apnea (OSA). Conventionally, the AHI is calculated from breathing signals recorded during a polysomnography (PSG). However, we aimed to utilize only the blood oxygen saturation (SpO₂) signal.

4.2.3.1.1 Methodology

The aim was to export SpO₂ signals and manual annotations from PSG recordings. The machine learning algorithms were aimed to be trained with short SpO₂ segments to estimate the AHI and to classify patients to have OSA or not. After confirming that these calculations can be performed on the cloud, the case was aimed to be repeated with encrypted data.

4.2.3.1.2 Data

Raw SpO₂ signals and information on the manually calculated AHI. We aim to start with utilizing open-source data and further collect PSG recordings prospectively. The planned data formats were .csv, .xls, .txt, .html, and .edf.

4.2.3.1.3 Technical requirements

Capacity to:

- process full night SpO₂ signals with sampling frequency of 10Hz;
- utilize double precision floating point values;
- utilize data with size of 200 MB;

4.2.3.1.4 Output

Exact value of the AHI and the severity of OSA.

4.2.3.2 Estimation of sleep stages and respiratory events from PSG recordings

Aim of this task was to estimate sleep stages and detect respiratory events from PSG recordings on the cloud.

4.2.3.2.1 Methodology

The aim was to export SpO₂, electroencephalography (EEG), nasal pressure, oronasal thermocouple, photoplethysmography (PPG), and respiratory effort signals from original PSG recordings to the .edf format. The data was aimed to be uploaded to the cloud and three different models be utilized:

- Model 1: SpO2 and PPG signals used as input;
- Model 2: SpO2, PPG, and nasal pressure signals used as input;
- Model 3: SpO2, nasal pressure, EEG (C4-M1 channel), oronasal thermocouple, and the sum of thoracic and abdominal respiratory inductance plethysmography belts signals used as input.

The aim was to utilize deep learning-based algorithms previously developed for simultaneous estimation of sleep stages and detection of respiratory events (doi: 10.1109/TBME.2022.3225268). The source code for the models is available at <https://github.com/rikuhuttunen/psg-simultscoring-models>. After confirming that above-mentioned calculations can be performed on the cloud, they will be repeated with encrypted data.

4.2.3.2.2 Data

Raw SpO2, PPG, nasal pressure, EEG (C4-M1 channel), oronasal thermocouple, and the sum of thoracic and abdominal respiratory inductance plethysmography belts signals. We aimed to start with utilizing open source data and further collect PSG recordings prospectively. Data formats to be tested can include but are not limited to: .csv, .xls, .txt, .html, .edf.

4.2.3.2.3 Technical requirements

Capacity to:

- process full night PSG recordings with sampling frequency of 1024Hz;
- utilize double precision floating point values;
- utilize data with size of 100 GB.

4.2.3.2.4 Output

Sleep stages separately for each 30 second epoch and probability for each sampling point whether they contain an apnea, hypopnea, or no-event.

4.2.3.3 Automatic exportation of PSG signals

The aim was to enable automatic exportation of sleep software-specific data formats to widely used .edf format in the cloud.

4.2.3.3.1 Methodology

The aim was to utilize previously developed stand-alone software for data exportation (doi: 10.1038/s41598-022-19892-0, <https://zenodo.org/record/7107966>).

4.2.3.3.2 Data

We aimed to start with utilizing open source full PSG data and further collect PSG recordings prospectively. Data formats to be tested can include but are not limited to: .csv, .xls, .txt, .html, .edf.

4.2.3.3.3 Technical requirements

Capacity to:

- process full night PSG recordings with sampling frequency of 1024Hz;
- utilize double precision floating point values;
- utilize data with size of 100 GB.

An additional requirement was the possibility to install sleep scoring software and user interface to the cloud. Furthermore, the stand-alone software would have needed to be re-coded to understand encrypted data.

4.2.3.3.4 Output

Fully automatic platform for exportation of PSG recordings to .edf format.

4.2.3.4 Estimation of presence of desaturations in short segments

The aim of this task was to simplify the task 4.1.3.1. We aim to classify short SpO2 signal segments based on whether those contain a desaturation or not.

4.2.3.4.1 Methodology

We aim to export SpO2 signals from PSG recordings. The SpO2 data will be split into five minute segments, values rounded to integers, and uploaded to the cloud. Machine learning algorithms will be used to classify SpO2 signals segments into two classes: containing a desaturation and no desaturations. We aim to implement a one-layer fully connected neural network.

4.2.3.4.2 Data

For this task we will make use of the SIESTA dataset (doi: 10.1109/IEMBS.2011.6092052)

- The SIESTA dataset contains 669 SpO2 signals from whole night PSG recordings in .edf format. From these 399 .edfs were used.
- Each signal has a sampling frequency between 1 - 256Hz.
- Data points are 2-byte integers.
- The SpO2 signals were preprocessed in the following ways to meet the constraints of the models provided by TUNI (see sections 4.1.3 and 5.1.1):
 - downsampled to 1Hz,

- Desaturations were automatically scored with ABOSA software (DOI:10.1016/j.cmpb.2022.107120). Minimum criteria for desaturation depth were set to be 3% and 4%, and minimum duration 10 seconds,
- Quantised to 5 bit integer. This was achieved by scaling the signal values between 0 and 31 (71->1, 100->30). Original values <71 were scaled to 0 and values >100 as 31. Thus, values 0 and 31 can be considered as artefacts.
- Signals were split into segments of 300 data points each. This equates to 5-minute per segment. The last segments of each recording were excluded as they are most often <5 minutes.
- Each segment having at least one value of 0 or 31 were removed as segments were considered to contain artefacts.
- In case a desaturation was split into two segments, both segments were excluded.

4.2.3.4.3 Technical requirements

All cloud resources must be provided by GWDG³. These resources include, but are not limited to, OpenStack⁴ based computing infrastructure, managed database services, s3 compatible object storage and single sign-on with OAUTH2/OpenID Connect. XNAT (doi: 10.1385/NL:5:1:11) must be used for data management: all signals, annotations, and processing artefacts must be catalogued by XNAT.

XNAT must be used for data access control: XNAT and its associated authentication and authorization mechanisms must be used to manage access to the data by user's and other software components. The automatic annotation software must support containerised execution with docker.

4.2.3.4.4 Functional Requirements

- It is necessary that the solution can be used regardless of the sleep recording software or device used to analyse or collect the data.
- Encryption should be possible also regardless of the number or quality of signals in sleep recordings.
- The solution should include a user-friendly user interface and be readily usable in the clinical (operational) environment by clinical practitioners.

4.2.3.4.5 Performance requirements

³ Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH Göttingen

⁴ OpenStack Cloud platform: <https://openstack.org>

- Time of transmission and of processing is an important requirement and should be in the range of a couple of minutes for a sleep recording. Ideally this should be not more than 5 minutes.
- Must support a modest amount of concurrent user sessions on reasonably priced cloud resources.

4.2.3.4.6 Privacy requirements

Encryption should be applied to all signals, and the report including results from the sleep analysis, if transmitted as well.

4.2.3.5 Calculation of hypoxic load from short segments of SpO2 signal

This task is a continuum from 4.1.3.4. The aim of this task was to calculate several desaturation metrics from short segments of encrypted SpO2 signals in the cloud.

4.2.3.5.1 Methodology

First, we aim to export SpO2 signals from PSG recordings. The SpO2 data was aimed to be split into five minutes segments, values rounded to integers, and uploaded to the cloud. Two types of calculations were aimed to be performed:

- Case 1: Desaturation metrics calculated from previously annotated desaturation events.
- Case 2: Desaturation events were aimed to be automatically annotated from raw SpO2 signal segments and desaturation metrics calculated based on the automatically detected desaturation events.

Automatic annotation of desaturation events was aimed to be performed by modifying the previously developed ABOSA software (doi: 10.1016/j.cmpb.2022.107120, <https://zenodo.org/record/6962129>). Desaturation metrics calculated on the cloud were aimed to be compared to those calculated locally. After confirming that above-mentioned calculations can be performed on the cloud, both cases were aimed to be repeated with encrypted data.

4.2.3.5.2 Data

The same data will be used as in 4.1.3.4.2.

4.2.3.5.3 Technical Requirements

In addition to the technical requirements described in 4.1.3.4.3., we require a capacity to:

- process full night SpO2 signals with sampling frequency 10Hz,
- utilize double precision floating point values
- utilize data with size of 100 MB

4.2.3.5.4 Output

Desaturation metrics in a table.

4.2.3.6 Calculation of sleep fragmentation from hypnograms

The aim was to calculate sleep quality metrics from hypnograms. In hypnograms, full night EEG information is squeezed to 30-second long sleep stages. Sleep stages can be classified to wake, rapid eye movement (REM) sleep, and non-REM sleep. Non-REM sleep can be further classified to sleep stages N1, N2, and N3.

4.2.3.6.1 Methodology

First, the aim was to export hypnograms from original, manually annotated PSG recordings (EEG). The hypnogram data was aimed to be transformed to integers and uploaded to the cloud. Calculated metrics include percentage of sleep stages, number of sleep stage transitions, latencies to sleep, deep sleep, REM sleep, wake after sleep onset, and sleep efficiency.

The code to calculate these metrics from hypnograms was aimed to be made. After confirming that above-mentioned calculations can be performed on the cloud, the calculations were aimed to be repeated with encrypted data.

4.2.3.6.2 Data

We aimed to start with utilizing open source full PSG data and further collect PSG recordings prospectively. Data formats to be tested can include but are not limited to: .csv, .xls, .txt, .html, .edf. One hypnogram contains around 700-900 integers in .txt file.

4.2.3.6.3 Technical requirements

Capacity to:

- process vector with 700-900 integers;
- utilize data with size of 1000 KB.

4.2.3.6.4 Output

Sleep quality metrics in a table.

5 HARPOCRATES Toolbox Architecture

5.1 HARPOCRATES Enabler Library

5.1.1 Privacy Preserving ML (PervPPML) through HHE

5.1.1.1 Functionality

We designed PervPPML, a model that enables efficient processing of encrypted data by an unauthorised entity, treating it as unencrypted. It consists of three protocols: 2PervPPML, 3PervPPML, and TrustedPervPPML to support Data Analysts, Trusted Execution Environment (TEE), and multi-user scenarios. The main components of these protocols are:

- **Users:** They generate a unique symmetric key locally and encrypt data such as medical images or one dimensional, time-series ECG data for analysis. The users are responsible for protecting their data and initiating the encryption process. For additional privacy enhancing steps, the user may add noise to their data with the use of differential privacy to obscure the true values of their inputs.
- **Data Analysts:** They own an ML model and are interested in learning the output of ML operations on the encrypted data stored at the CSP. The Analysts want to obtain information while maintaining data privacy. As the Analysts are the owner of the ML models, they will provide the correct model for the corresponding input data, either time-series or images.
- **Cloud Service Provider (CSP)** It is responsible for gathering symmetrically encrypted data from multiple users. The CSP is tasked with converting the symmetrically encrypted data into homomorphic ciphertexts and, upon request, operate on encrypted data using the encrypted model provided by the Analyst and the converted data provided by the User.
- **Trusted Execution Environment (TEE):** It is responsible for securely sharing results from the learning phase of our protocol with a requesting party as well as securely generating the keys to avoid a single party having full access to the encrypted data.

While the User and CSP are integral parts of all three protocols, the Analyst is involved in 3PervPPML and TrustedPervPPML. TEE, on the other hand, is exclusively employed within the TrustedPervPPML protocol.

5.1.1.2 Interfaces

Basic command line outputs or text file representations of the command line outputs are used for debugging purposes. However, the main internal interactions between the components taking part in the above protocols happen via Remote Procedure Call. Specifically, relevant functionality of the above User, Analyst and CSP components have been exposed as part of an interface implemented via the gRPC framework; the data exchanged through those interfaces is serialised as Protocol Buffers. These technologies were chosen to achieve better

performance when compared to other types of interfaces, such as those implemented as JSON/REST. Nonetheless, JSON over HTTP/REST will be used to expose functionalities of those components with non-stringent performance requirements whose access is required by other components of the system.

5.1.1.3 Input

One dimensional time-series ECG data. The data should be provided in standard data types, easily accessible through C++ or Python programming languages.

5.1.1.4 Output

A vector of binary classification outputs.

5.1.1.5 Limitations

Our PervPPML model currently supports a simple linear regression ML model with limited operations (addition and multiplication) and only accepts integer data types, lacking support for floating-point numbers in its current state.

5.1.2 Privacy Preserving ML through FE

5.1.2.1 Functionality

We work on an FE scheme that features 3 parties: user(s), server and data analyst(s).

- **Users** can encrypt their hypnograms (i.e., a vector of integers between 0 and 9) independently and store them on a server. This server does not have to be trusted.
- **Server.** After checking the credentials of a **Data Analyst**, the server provides a specific decryption key which gives access to the number of appearances of each integer in the hypnogram.

We intend to extend the capabilities of this protocol in the future by extending the set of functions allowed by the scheme: counting the number of appearances of each integer in a row, the number of transitions between two integers and make our technique compatible with traditional inner product and quadratic protocols.

5.1.2.2 Interfaces

Basic command line outputs or text file representations of the command line outputs. As the protocol is developed the operations of the program will be distributed through the use of different interfaces, a possible implementation of this would be similar to the method used in PervPPML. Namely, the core functionality would possibly be implemented via Remote Procedure Calls and would utilise gRPC or other interface implementations, such as JSON/REST, depending on the performance requirements.

5.1.2.3 Input Format

A vector of integers of arbitrary size. In our use-case, a few hundred integers between 0 and 9. No floating points.

5.1.2.4 Output Format

A vector of integers (the number of appearances of each integer).

5.1.2.5 Limitations

Traditional operations are limited to inner product (i.e., addition) and quadratic polynomials (i.e., single multiplication). The plaintext space is limited to integers. FE often requires trusted authority.

5.1.3 Privacy Preserving FL Module

5.1.3.1 Functionality

A Federated Learning enabler has a set of functionalities designed to facilitate decentralised Machine Learning. It operates under the principles of Federated Learning, where a model is trained across multiple decentralised edge devices or servers holding local data samples, without exchanging them. The enabler provides Federated Learning infrastructure enhanced with an additional layer of security utilising fully homomorphic encryption. In order to exclude any possibility of reverse engineering partial models dispatched by collaborator nodes during the enabler's aggregation phase of Federated Learning effort, an aggregator node will be considered a non-trusted party. Collaborator nodes will dispatch their calculated partial models encrypted to the aggregator, where they will be aggregated into a global model by using the Homomorphic Encryption. Global model will remain encrypted. Only parties that have key at their disposal will have insight into results of collaborative training effort.

The key features of this building block are as follows:

- **Data Localization:** The component ensures that data remains on its original device, thereby maintaining privacy and adhering to data protection regulations.
- **Model Training and Aggregation:** It facilitates the training of local models on edge devices or nodes. These local models are then aggregated into a global model, which iteratively improves with each training round.
- **Security and Privacy:** Incorporates advanced security protocols to protect the models and the training process. This includes encryption techniques and possibly differential privacy measures to prevent data leakage.

Figure 1 Privacy Preserving Federated Learning Module

5.1.3.2 Interfaces

Module infrastructure will provide a REST API on the relation researcher - central server, along with REST API and WebSockets on the relation central server - collaborator nodes. Both central server and collaborator nodes will have access to the docker repository where ML algorithms will be stored and deployed from.

Table 7 API Specification of the Privacy Preserving Federated Learning Module

GET /task	List all tasks that your organisation is authorised to see
GET /task/{id}	Return the task by ID
POST /task	Creates a new task within a collaboration. If no ids are given the task is sent to all organisations.
DELETE /task/{id}	Deletes the task
GET /task/{id}/result	Return results of the task process
GET /user	List all users
POST /user	Create user
DELETE /user/{id}	Delete user by id
GET /user/{id}	Get user by id

GET /collaboration	Returns a list of collaborations your organisation participates
POST /collaboration	Create collaboration for number of organisation
DELETE /collaboration/{id}	Delete collaboration by ID
GET /collaboration/{id}	Get collaboration information by ID
PATCH /collaboration/{id}	Update collaboration by ID
DELETE /collaboration/{id}/node	Remove specific node by ID from collaboration
GET /collaboration/{id}/node	List nodes in collaboration.
POST /collaboration/{id}/node	Add node to collaboration
DELETE /collaboration/{id} /organisation	Remove organisation from collaboration
GET /collaboration/{id} /organisation	Returns organisations that participate in the collaboration
POST /collaboration/{id} /organisation	Add organisation to collaboration
GET /collaboration/{id}/task	List tasks from collaboration

5.1.3.3 Input Format

On the researcher - central server relation, input is REST API request detailing the specifics of the collaborative training effort to be executed. On the node, input will be a request from the central server with the specifics of the effort and the docker container with the algorithm to be

executed. Docker containers will receive input in the form of agreed upon and correctly formatted data to train the model on.

5.1.3.4 Output Format

Entire process will come to fruition with an encrypted, trained model. Only those parties that have keys at their disposal will have insight into the results of model training.

5.1.3.5 Limitations

5.1.4 Privacy Preserving ML with DP-based data synthetization

5.1.4.1 Functionality

A membership inference attack is a type of privacy breach where an attacker tries to determine if a particular data record was included in the training dataset of a target Machine Learning model by querying the model itself. This poses a significant security risk for ML models as it can lead to the exposure of user information and sensitive data. To address this vulnerability, this enabler focuses on creating Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning models that are immune to membership inference attacks. This is achieved through the utilisation of differential privacy-based data synthesis. The synthetic data generated by our approach is designed to be non-invertible. Additionally, we strive to ensure that the victim model maintains a high level of performance and utility.

5.1.4.2 Interfaces

We are offering an open-source Python code-based API/Repository that includes a variety of functions for our partners to utilise. This API/Repository allows for the definition of machine models on a case-by-case basis, accommodating different requirements and scenarios.

5.1.4.3 Input Format

The model that is wished to be privacy-preserved.

5.1.4.4 Output Format

We are going to provide a scheme/framework. The format can be an API service or source code.

5.1.4.5 Limitations

Intended to be demonstrated with a data set from the threat intelligence case, but not as part of project demonstrator.

5.1.5 Robust FL with weight tuning

5.1.5.1 Functionality

The primary objective of this component is to enhance the robustness of Federated Learning (FL) setups by ensuring that the machine learning models used in FL are resilient against adversarial attacks, particularly targeted poisoning attacks (also known as backdoor attacks). In a poisoning attack, the attacker injects malicious data into the model's training dataset to manipulate its learning process and induce undesirable behavior.

Our aim is to introduce a robust aggregation rule that specifically defends against targeted data and model poisoning attacks. This is achieved by assigning appropriate weights to the contributions of different clients within the FL framework. By doing so, we can minimize the impact of compromised or malicious clients on the model updates.

5.1.5.2 Interfaces

We are offering an open-source Python code-based API/Repository that includes a variety of functions for our partners to utilize. This API/Repository allows for the definition of machine models on a case-by-case basis, accommodating different requirements and scenarios.

5.1.5.3 Input Format

The model that is wished to be robust against poisoning attack.

5.1.5.4 Output Format

We are going to provide a scheme/framework. The format can be an API service or source code.

5.1.5.5 Limitations

Will be demonstrated with a data set from the threat intelligence case, but not as part of the project demonstrator.

5.1.6 Privacy Preserving Machine Learning with Homomorphic Encryption

This enabler supports Privacy-Preserving Federated Learning. Privacy preservation is primarily achieved through secure aggregation of weights from locally trained models.

5.1.6.1 Functionality

The module allows collaborative model training over data distributed across several contributing parties. The module is built as an extension of the Flower framework for federated learning research (<https://github.com/adap/flower>).

5.1.6.2 Interfaces

The module and its operations can be invoked through the following interfaces:

- Command line from the terminal;
- REST API. The specification of the REST API will be defined in the final release version of the software.

5.1.6.3 Input Format

The module consumes input in the form of text files containing arrays of comma separated values for local model training.

5.1.6.4 Output Format

The module produces output in the form of text files containing arrays of comma separated values with predicted values.

5.1.6.5 Limitations

In the current implementation, secure aggregation of weights from locally trained models is achieved using homomorphic encryption. This approach introduces certain performance and computational costs. Other secure aggregation approaches will be investigated in the upcoming versions of the module. **This component** will be demonstrated with a data set from the threat intelligence case.

5.2 Support components

5.2.1 Storage Frontend (MinIO)

MinIO is a High-Performance Object Storage released under GNU Affero General Public License v3.0. It is API compatible with Amazon S3 cloud storage service. MinIO is used to build high-performance infrastructure for Machine Learning, analytics and application data workloads⁵. A MinIO single-node installation can be deployed on a cloud Virtual Machine to simulate a generic dataset storage setup.

5.2.2 Certificate Authority

A custom root Certificate Authority (CA) can be deployed on a cloud VM, simulating a customer-controlled or customer-approved (3rd-party) trusted CA. The public key certificate of the CA can be provisioned as a trusted to the MinIO deployment to enable certificate-based authentication. This way, MinIO verifies the certificate endorser and signature before providing access to a specific bucket or object.

5.2.3 MiCADO Deployer

MiCADO is the primary execution engine, available for facilitating the deployment of demonstrator applications and other toolbox components. MiCADO was originally developed

⁵ <https://github.com/minio/minio>

D3.1 Technical Requirements, Architecture and Testing Plan

in the European Horizon 2020 COLA (Cloud Orchestration at the Level of Application) Project. Built on the open-source Kubernetes orchestration platform, MiCADO started life as an application-level cloud orchestrator, but over time it has been extended with support for edge, enabling orchestration across the cloud to edge continuum.

The MiCADO platform is a high-level orchestrator that offers a simplified interface to a prepared Kubernetes cluster and a cloud provisioning tool. MiCADO also adds its own features, including cloud-agnostic auto-scaling and additional layers of security. The Kubernetes cluster in MiCADO is configured with sensible defaults and add-ons that are ready to use, like the Kubernetes Dashboard and a Prometheus-Grafana monitoring stack.

Two different cloud provisioning tools are available in MiCADO - Hashicorp's Terraform, and a smaller tool called Occopus. These provisioning tools enable MiCADO to dynamically provision cloud infrastructure to host deployed applications. An internal component called the Policy Keeper enforces user-defined scaling rules to dynamically scale both containers and cloud resources at runtime. To bring orchestration to the edge, MiCADO relies on two separate open-source CNCF projects interchangeably - KubeEdge and K3S - to extend the Kubernetes cluster towards one or more edge devices.

The interface to MiCADO is the Application Description Template (ADT) - a deployment descriptor that describes the application containers, cloud and/or edge infrastructure, and enforceable runtime decisions related to scalability, monitoring, and security. The ADT is based on v1.x of the OASIS TOSCA (Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications) Specification. An internal component called the Submitter exposes a REST API and is responsible for interpreting an ADT and communicating information to Kubernetes and the cloud orchestrators to realise a successful deployment.

Figure 1 Architecture of the MiCADO Cloud to Edge Orchestrator

The architecture of MiCADO is visualised in Figure 1. At the left of the figure, the ADT is sent in a POST request to the REST API of the Submitter component. The Submitter disseminates information in the ADT to Kubernetes, the cloud provisioner, the monitoring stack, the Policy Keeper and edge-related components. The cloud provisioner deploys and manages cloud worker instances, ensuring they are prepared with monitoring components and a container runtime. Kubernetes deploys and manages containers to these cloud workers. The Policy Keeper enforces any scaling rules, calling Kubernetes or the cloud provisioner as needed to scale a resource up or down. KubeEdge connects any edge devices to the cluster, creating additional workers where Kubernetes can deploy containers. Finally, the monitoring stack visualises CPU, memory and network metrics across the cluster, plus any application-specific metrics the user may have configured.

5.2.4 User Interface

A user interface may optionally be added to the HARPOCRATES architecture. It can facilitate interaction of end-users with the HARPOCRATES toolbox as well as help in demonstration tasks. Currently there is no user interface in scope.

5.2.5 Attestation Service

An attestation service may *optionally* be added to perform third-party attestation. The attestation service is SaaS-based implementation of a trust authority providing remote verification of the trustworthiness of a processing environment based on attestation and policy. The attestation service may initially support verification of the trustworthiness of several vendor CPU-based TEE implementations. It can be extended with future support for IPU, GPU, platform roots of trust, and beyond. Verification of trustworthiness by an independent

authority provides increased assurances to users, along with a security foundation for confidential computing to enable new usages in AI, multi-party compute, and federated learning. Moreover, an attestation service enables the HARPOCRATES component toolbox to securely scale and move workloads across several independent cloud environments.

5.3 High-level Architectural Overview of HARPOCRATES Toolbox

The HARPOCRATES architecture includes three conceptual domains: (i) the cloud compute domain that primarily contains an *enabler library* of solutions, (ii) the client domain that contains input data, along with local compute components and additional functionality to support interaction with the enablers, and (iii) third-party cloud services that provide ancillary functions such as user interface, attestation service and cryptographic key storage. Figure 2 depicts a overview of the HARPOCRATES architecture.

The *enabler library* is the central component of the HARPOCRATES architecture. It represents a collection of enablers developed by technical partners in WP1 and WP2 with to address use case requirements. Enablers are made available as self-contained software, delivered in container images with well-defined and documented interfaces. The enabler library contains support software for (i) sandboxing of the enablers and (ii) proxying their communication with external data sources and services.

Figure 2 Architectural overview of the Harpocrates Toolbox

D3.1 Technical Requirements, Architecture and Testing Plan

The **client domain** contains input data, along with local compute components and additional functionality to support interaction with the enablers. The HARPOCRATES architecture is oblivious to the choice of the backend for data storage. However, to ensure wide compatibility with state-of-the-art solutions, it is expected that data will be exposed through an S3 REST API⁶. For the reference implementation, this can be achieved using the MinIO storage front-end⁷. Along with that, the client domain may include ancillary enabler-specific software that enables interaction between the client domain and the compute domain. However, the functionality and purpose of this client software - as well as communication protocol of choice and API - varies from enabler to enabler.

The **third-party cloud services domain** includes optional services ancillary functions such as user interface, attestation service and cryptographic key storage (Key Value). These services may or may not be included depending on the specific context of the deployment and requirements of the enabler. Moreover, additional services are likely to be required in the case of a high-TRL deployment of the enabler. The third-party services may interact with either components in the client domain, cloud compute domain, or both. They may as well interact with the support components such as the Certificate Authority or the MiCADO deployer, which were introduced earlier in Section 5.2.

⁶ S3 REST API: <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/AmazonS3/latest/API/Welcome.html>

⁷ MinIO high-performance S3 compatible object store: <https://min.io/>

6 Testing and Evaluation Plan

WP3 depends on inputs from other WPs, namely the technical enablers of the HARPOCRATES toolbox designed and developed in WP1-WP2, as well as on the demonstrators and test bed designed and developed in WP4. Accordingly, the initial specification of the enablers was used as an “input” for designing the integration process within WP3. The important milestone, which is of utmost importance for the integration and testing plans of WP3, is Milestone MS5 at M36 (“*HARPOCRATES Framework released*”). This milestone in turn relies upon the following milestones MS1 at M20 (“Design and implementation of HARPOCRATES HHE and FE schemes.”), MS2 at MS27 (“*Differential Privacy with Cryptography*”), and MS3 at M20 (“*Protocols for privacy- preserving training and features extraction*”). These milestones signify the delivery of the first versions of the enablers developed within the context of WP1-2. Upon finalising and reaching the milestone, WP3 partners will start integrating and testing, as described in the sections of this deliverable that follow below.

6.1 Testing methodology

HARPOCRATES adopts an agile testing approach⁸. This approach considers development and testing as two intertwined phases and not sequential (i.e. testing following development). This decision was dictated by the tight delivery dates of the enablers as well as the requirement for early integration before the demonstrators takes place.

⁸ L. Crispin and J. Gregory. Agile Testing: A Practical Guide for Testers and Agile Teams. Addison-Wesley Professional, 2009

Figure 3 Test methodology overview

With respect to the testing of enablers, following the generic methodology proposed in [9], Figure 3 presents a generic perspective of the integration, testing, and validation processes of enablers which will be adopted in HARPOCRATES. to produce the final HARPOCRATES enabler toolbox (the numbers refer to steps, as described below, after the figure)

According to this generic methodology, this process is composed of the following major steps:

1. Individual unit testing.
2. Integration of individual units to implement the HARPOCRATES enabler toolbox.
3. Validation test of the components in the toolbox against the requirements.
4. First round of enabler toolbox testing.
5. Feedback to developers and implementation of corrective measures – quick individual unit testing against reported problems.
6. Integration of new individual unit modules.
7. Second round of final enabler toolbox testing.
8. Pilot operation and testing with a small group of real users.

In Figure 4 the testing process for each integrated module are presented to highlight how it is being done:

⁹ R. Pressman and B. Maxim. Software Engineering: A Practitioner’s Approach. McGraw-Hill Education, 8th Edition, 2014.

Figure 4 Test, Evaluation and Verification methodology

When it comes to system testing, we adopt Incremental testing, described below. In the given context, the term "low-level component" pertains to self-contained modules that carry out specific, relatively simple computations, while the term "high-level component" refers to modules that perform more intricate operations and rely on other modules for their functioning.

Incremental testing:

- **Top-Down testing:** The top-down testing methodology involves starting the integration and testing process from the highest-level components. This approach allows for the testing of the system's high-level parts, including data flows and interfaces. By beginning with the higher-level components, the reliance on drivers, which are test modules that invoke other modules, is minimised since most modules are already in place, particularly the high-level ones. However, as the lower-level modules are not yet available, stubs are required to provide inputs to the higher-level components being tested. These stubs will be determined later by the involved partners, taking into consideration the actual code of the tested modules, which is not currently accessible. Furthermore, the testing of the lower-level components is deferred to a later stage in the integration process, leaving limited time for corrective actions at the system level.
- **Bottom-Up testing:** In contrast to top-down testing, the bottom-up testing strategy starts the integration and testing process from the lower-level system components. This approach minimises the need for stubs and allows for the early identification of low-level issues before integration begins. However, more drivers are required to appropriately invoke the lower-level components since the higher-level components, which depend on the lower-level ones, are not yet available.
- **Sandwich Testing:** Also known as Hybrid Integration Testing, this approach combines the top-down and bottom-up approaches. With the sandwich testing methodology, lower level modules are tested in parallel while their integration progresses alongside the testing process,

with the integration itself being tested as well. This approach minimises the need for stubs and drivers. However, it is slightly less systematic compared to the top-down and bottom-up approaches and may require additional coordination efforts.

6.2 Enabler use case templates

Structured, incremental testing of enablers developed in Harpocrates will be done by exercising their functionality according to pre-defined *enabler use cases*. Note that these are different from the demonstrator use cases explored in the project – in particular, they are defined on a more granular level pertinent to each specific enabler. To prepare the tests, the enabler developers describe use case according to a pre-defined template, as described below. The enabler use case template consists of two main parts: (i) Use Case Identification, and (ii) Use Case Definition. These parts are further elaborated in the subsequent subsections, and it is necessary to define them for the test procedures applied to each of the systems outlined in the following Sections.

6.2.1 Part A: Use case identification

Table 8 Use case identification template

Use Case ID:			
Use Case Name:			
Created By:		Last Updated By:	
Date Created:		Date Last Updated:	

Use Case ID

Assign a unique incremental integer sequence number identifier to each use case. For example, use case IDs can be represented as CBIT_01 or ZEN_01.

Use Case Name

Provide a concise, results-oriented name for each use case that reflects the tasks the user needs to accomplish using the system. Use an action verb and a noun in the name. Examples include "User Registration to the HARPOCRATES enabler toolbox" or "HARPOCRATES Toolbox Setup."

Use Case History

Created By

Specify the name of the person who initially documented the use case.

Date Created

Enter the date when the use case was initially documented.

Last Updated By

Specify the name of the person who performed the most recent update to the use case description.

date Last Updated

Enter the date when the use case was last updated.

6.2.2 Part B: Use Case Definition

Table 9 Use case definition template

Actors:	
Description:	
Trigger:	
Preconditions:	
Postconditions:	
Normal Flow:	
Alternative Flows:	
Exceptions:	
Includes:	
Special Requirements:	
Legal Considerations:	

Assumptions:	
Notes and Issues:	

Actors

Identify the actors who interact with the system and perform the use cases to accomplish tasks. Actors can be individuals or entities external to the software system. Name the actor initiating the use case and any other actors participating in its completion.

Description

Provide a brief description of the purpose and outcome of the use case. This can include a high-level explanation of the sequence of actions and the expected outcome upon executing the use case.

Trigger

Identify the event that initiates the use case. It can be an external or system event that causes the use case to start or the first step in the normal flow.

Preconditions

List any activities or conditions that must be fulfilled before starting the use case. Number each precondition. For example:

- The user has been successfully authenticated.
- The user's mobile device has adequate protection against malware.

Postconditions

Describe the state of the system after completing the use case execution. Number each postcondition.

Normal Flow.

Provide a detailed description of the user actions and system responses that occur during the execution of the use case under normal conditions. Describe the sequential steps leading to achieving the goal stated in the use case name and description. Number the steps as "X.0", where "X" represents the Use Case ID.

Alternative Flows

Document other valid usage scenarios within the use case in this section. State the alternative flow and describe any deviations in the sequence of steps. Number each alternative flow as "X.Y", where "X" is the Use Case ID and "Y" is a sequence number for the alternative flow.

Exceptions

Describe any anticipated error conditions during the use case execution and specify how the system should respond. Also, define the system's response if the use case execution fails due

to unforeseen circumstances. If the use case results in a durable state change in a database or the outside world, indicate whether the change should be rolled back, completed correctly, partially completed with a known state, or left in an undetermined state due to the exception. Number each exception flow as "X.Y.E.Z", where "X" is the Use Case ID, "Y" indicates the normal (0) or alternative (>0) flow where the exception may occur, "E" represents an exception, and "Z" is a sequence number for the exceptions for the second exception in the normal flow of use case.

Includes

List any other use cases that are included or called by this use case. Common functionality shared among multiple use cases can be separated into a distinct use case included by those requiring that common functionality.

Special Requirements

Identify any additional requirements, such as non-functional requirements, specific to the use case that need to be addressed during design or implementation. These may include performance requirements or other quality attributes.

Legal Considerations

Identify any legal implications that must be considered for the use case.

Assumptions

List any assumptions made during the analysis that led to accepting this use case into the product description and writing the use case description.

Notes and Issues

List any additional comments, open issues, or TBDs (To Be Determined) related to the use case. Identify the responsible party for resolving each issue, the due date, and the ultimate resolution.

Please note that not all fields mentioned above may be applicable or necessary to fill in at this stage, as the tested modules are not yet available. However, these fields are provided for completeness and potential future use once the modules are ready for testing. In a subsequent version of this deliverable, after performing the tests and documenting the results, the use case definition tables described in this version will be updated accordingly.

6.3 Test Outcomes and Corrective Measures

Following exercising of the functionality of the enablers according to the specifications defined above, additional feedback from the HARPOCRATES demonstrator use cases will be utilised to implement corrective measures for the toolbox components under test before the integration phase. After each use case description, two sections will follow: one documenting the test results and another documenting the corrective measures taken.

DRAFT

7 Conclusion

This document provides a detailed description of the technical requirements, architecture, and testing plan for HARPOCRATES. The document includes an executive summary, introduction, background, methodology, and conclusion. The document outlines demonstrators: (i) exchange of threat intelligence information between two regional governments in EU member states and (ii) exchange of sleep research data between three research performing institutions located in three EU member states. Beyond introducing the demonstrators and their use cases and presenting their requirements, this document outlines the technological background used in the project and a description of the enablers developed by the technical partners in WP1 and WP2. These enablers will form the HARPOCRATES enabler library. Finally, the document describes the overall architecture HARPOCRATES enabler library on a level that allows its adoption for the HARPOCRATES demonstrators implementing their use cases. Overall, this document provides a comprehensive overview of the project, including the technical requirements, architecture, and testing plan. The document is intended for technical personnel involved in the project and provides a detailed guide for the development and testing of the project.

Annex 1: Threat Intelligence Demonstrator Use Case Descriptions

Use case 1: Detect an anomalous event signalling a potential attack

HARPOCRATES partner name: S2, SARGA, VENETO

Use case goal

Detect an anomalous event signalling a potential attack

Use Case Overview

With the Sysmon log data captured from users activity on their computers, a privacy-preserving model can be trained to discern normal from anomalous behaviour. With that model, a range of events can be tested against the model to identify if something different from expected has happened signalling a possible security incident.

Primary actor

The agent installed on each user computer, collecting log events and inspecting them for anomalies. During design time we will decide if the ML models reside completely on the cloud, locally or in a mixed way.

Secondary actor (s)

N/A

Assumptions Preconditions

A ML-privacy preserving anomaly detection model has been trained.

Business event

Automatically on each event, or alternatively over a period of time.

Use case description - main scenario

- One or a collection of events are collected by the agent;
- They are uploaded to the demonstrator Threat Intelligence platform;
- The events are verified against the anomaly detection model;
- A signal is produced if an anomaly is detected;
- That signal is shown on a management dashboard.

Use case description - alternative scenario

N/A

Use case failure scenario

N/A

Input summary

Sysmon log event or structured data based on them

Post-conditions and acceptance criteria

A simulated attack which suspicious behaviour on a computer is detected, i.e. a powershell process created by a Microsoft word process that connects to the internet.

Annex 2: Sleep Medicine Demonstrator Use Case Descriptions

Use case 1: Estimation of the number of desaturation events from SpO2 signal segments

HARPOCRATES partner name: UEF, CRT, UMG

Use case goal

To estimate the number/existence of the desaturations in 5-minute segments of the blood oxygen saturation (SpO2) signal.

Use Case Overview

Nocturnal breathing cessations cause transient drops, i.e. desaturations in SpO2 levels. In this use case, we will estimate the presence (binary; yes/no) and the number (discrete) of desaturations in each 5-min segment of a SpO2 signal by utilizing simple DL models.

Primary actor

Researcher runs the DL models locally with unencrypted data and in a cloud with encrypted data and compares the results.

Secondary actor (s)

None

Assumptions Preconditions

The limitations of HHE encryption schemes are not too harsh for accurate enough DL models to be constructed.

Business event

N/A

Use case description - main scenario

The presence (binary; yes/no) of desaturation event(s) in each 5-min segment of SpO2 signal.

Use case description - alternative scenario

The number (discrete) of desaturation events in each 5-min segment.

Use case failure scenario

Accurate enough DL models cannot be constructed due to the limitations of HHE schemes leading to suboptimal model accuracies.

Input summary

SpO2 signal segments are in .txt format. However, if needed, the data can be transformed in numerous different formats, such as .csv or .xls.

Post-conditions and acceptance criteria

Data must be trackable in the cloud. Access to the data must be controlled and followed. There needs to be the possibility to remove data (or parts of it) from the cloud.

Use case 2: Calculation of hypoxic load from SpO2 signals**HARPOCRATES partner name: UEF, CR, UMG****Use case goal**

To characterise the severity of hypoxic load in each 5-min segment of a SpO2 signal.

Use Case Overview

This use case is a continuum of the previous use case. In this use case, the severity of hypoxic load in each 5-min segment is characterised with more comprehensive metrics, such as areas, depths, and durations of individual desaturations. For this, DL models will be developed.

Primary actor

Researcher runs the DL models locally with unencrypted data and in a cloud with encrypted data and compares the results.

Secondary actor (s)

None

Assumptions Preconditions

The calculation of more comprehensive metrics from the desaturations to describe the severity of hypoxic load is slightly more complex than in the previous use case. Therefore, the limitations of HHE encryption schemes for the DL models are even more relevant in this use case.

Business event

N/A

Use case description - main scenario

The severity of hypoxic load is calculated from previously annotated desaturations from which different metrics are calculated:

- The total areas formed by the desaturations in each 5-min segment
- The total durations of desaturations in each 5-min segment

Use case description - alternative scenario

The detection of desaturations can be implemented to the algorithms, i.e. the severity of hypoxic load can be calculated from desaturations that are automatically detected. From these automatically detected desaturations the same metrics as in the main scenario can be calculated.

Use case failure scenario

Accurate enough DL models cannot be constructed due to the limitations of HHE schemes leading to suboptimal model accuracies.

Input summary

SpO2 signal segments are in .txt format. However, if needed, the data can be transformed in numerous different formats, such as .csv or .xls.

Post-conditions and acceptance criteria

Data must be trackable in the cloud. Access to the data must be controlled and followed. There needs to be the possibility to remove data (or parts of it) from the cloud.

Use case 3: Calculation of sleep fragmentation from hypnograms

HARPOCRATES partner name: UEF, TUNI, CRT, UMG

Use case goal

To characterise the degree of sleep fragmentation with numerous different metrics derived from the hypnograms.

Use Case Overview

Different sleep disorders, such as sleep apnea and insomnia disrupt and fragment sleep. In this use case, we will quantify the degree of sleep fragmentation based on the hypnograms. Algorithms will be developed to describe the sleep fragmentation with numerous different parameters.

Primary actor

Researcher develops the algorithms which are run locally with unencrypted data and in a cloud with encrypted data after which the results are compared.

Secondary actor (s)

None

Assumptions Preconditions

HHE schemes are capable of executing nonlinear operations (e.g. comparisons; <, >, ==).

Business event

N/A

Use case description - main scenario

Sleep fragmentation is characterized with numerous parameters, such as percentage of sleep in each sleep stage, number of sleep stage transitions, and how much the patient is awake within the night.

Use case description - alternative scenario

N/A

Use case failure scenario

Currently HHE schemes do not support nonlinear operations. Therefore, currently this use case cannot be executed. However, if significant progress is achieved during the HARPOCRATES project related to the supported operations, this use case becomes relevant.

Input summary

Hypnograms are in .txt format. However, if needed, the data can be transformed in numerous different formats, such as. .csv or .xls.

Post-conditions and acceptance criteria

Data must be trackable in the cloud. Access to the data must be controlled and followed. There needs to be the possibility to remove data (or parts of it) from the cloud.